

New blast-resistant cultures from India

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TKM9, a high yielding, early-maturing cosmopolitan red rice released January 1978, is popular in Tamil Nadu. During navarai 1979-80 (December-January to March-April) TKM9 showed 60-70% blast incidence. From this crop, 10 single plants exhibiting field resistance to blast (0 to 5%) were isolated and studied. In 1980-81 preliminary yield trials,

Performance of blast-resistant lines at Paddy Experiment Station, Tirurkuppam, India.

Culture	Parentage	Growth duration (days)	Grain yield (t/ha)	% yield increase over TKM9	Blast (%)
TM8089	TKM9 selection	120	3.8	112	5.0
TM8090	TKM9 selection	117	3.7	109	10.5
TM8091	TKM9 selection	120	4.1	121	4.5
TKM9	TKM7/IR8	117	3.4	100	21.5
CD (P = 0.05)			0.5		

three of these selections showed promising yield and blast resistance.

In comparative yield trials during navarai 1981-82 they yielded better and showed less blast incidence than TKM9

(see table). These cultures are being tested in multilocation trials. The best variety will be released for wider cultivation when yield potential and blast resistance are confirmed. *h*

Bacterial stalk rot, new rice disease in Bangladesh

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Bacterial stalk rot or foot rot of rice caused by *Erwinia chrysanthemi* pv. *chrysanthemi* Burkholder, McFadden, and Dimock was observed in Bangladesh for the first time 27 April 1982 at the BRRI Joydebpur farm on breeding line BR161-2B-23 transplanted in an irrigated field. Of 300 varieties or lines in the field, 27 were heavily infected.

Bacterium from ooze extracted from a severely infected tiller was isolated in PSA (peptone-sucrose-agar) medium. Different dilutions of the ooze were used for pure culture isolation. The single colony isolate was multiplied on King's medium B. Pathogenicity was tested by

inoculating test plants twice. The BR161-2B-23 isolate was tested on Taichung Native 1 (TNI) plants at boot stage, reisolated from the inoculated TNI, and retested on the same variety at early tillering to midtillering stages. In both tests, plants showed the same symptoms as the field sample.

Leaf sheaths of infected plants were brown and water soaked. Leaves were brownish yellow and drooped from rotted dark brown leaf sheaths. Basal internode tissue rotted and had a foul smell. Dark brown color on the sheath just beneath the leaf juncture or ligule is the initial symptom. The disease spread to closed young leaves, culms (nodes and internodes), and the crown. Roots became rotten and dark brown to blackish and had a foul smell. Rotten young leaves and culms smelled the same.

Artificial inoculation of the bacterial suspension (10^8 to 10^{10} cells/ml water) by injecting TNI plants at tillering stage,

maximum tillering stage, and boot stage produced initial symptoms (water-soaked lesions around inoculation points) in 16 hours. When the plants were at maximum tillering to boot stage the youngest leaves started to wilt after 48 hours. Within 3-4 days lesion length sometimes extended through 60-80% of the sheath. At early tillering the dark brown lesion was restricted to the point of inoculation on the outer sheath, but even the youngest closed leaves and culms (nodes and internodes) became infected. Within a week, the leaves of inoculated plants turned brown and plants wilted and died.

The causal organism, *E. chrysanthemi* pv. *chrysanthemi*, was confirmed by performing physiological diagnostic tests such as anaerobic growth, gas formation from D-glucose, growth in 5% NaCl, no blue pigment on yeast extract-dextrose calcium carbonate (YDC) medium, and brown pigment formation on PSA. *h*

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Insect resistance

The Malayan black bug *Scotinophara coarctata* (F.) [Hemiptera: Pentatomidae]: a new rice pest in the Philippines

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Four species of *Scotinophara* black bugs have been recorded in the Philippines — *S. cinerea* Le Guill. (Hasegawa, 1971) (*S. cinerea* is now synonymous with *S. coarctata*), *S. scotti* Horvath (Miyamoto, Japan, pers. comm.), *S. ochracea*

(Dist.), and *S. lurida* (Burm.) (Wongsiri, 1975) — but none have been reported as rice pests.

In February 1982, a new pest, the Malayan black bug *S. coarctata* (F.) (confirmed by Miyamoto) was found Bonobono, Batarasa, South Palawan. major outbreak followed during March-June, and spread toward central and